

Cyberbullying and self-concept in physical education school children

Ciberacoso y autoconcepto en escolares de Educación Física

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Abstract

Cyberbullying is a highly complex phenomenon resulting from the continuous and inexhaustible evolution of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). Factors are sought that are associated with this phenomenon as emotional self-efficacy, self-esteem and empathy have been shown to be. Thus, the objectives were: (1) to analyze scores on the Cyberbullying (ECIPQ) and Self-Concept (AF-5) questionnaires as a function of gender and educational stage, (2) to explore the correlations between cyberbullying and self-concept as a function of gender and educational stage. A cross-sectional study was designed with a total of 1155 participants, 48.8% boys and 51.2% girls, where 75.9% studied compulsory secondary education (CSE) and 24.1% Baccalaureate. Significant inverse mean correlations were shown between cyberbullying dimensions with total self-concept for both sexes ($r = -0.15 - -0.11$; $p < 0.01$) and for CSE students ($r = -0.13 - -0.12$; $p < 0.01$), with these correlations being observed in high school students for cybervictimization ($r = -0.14$; $p = 0.02$). Significant inverse mean correlations were observed between academic ($r = -0.25 - -0.22$; $p < 0.01 - 0.04$) and family self-concept ($r = -0.27 - -0.26$; $p < 0.01$) with cyberbullying for both sexes and both educational stages. Direct and significant mean correlations were also shown between emotional self-concept and cyberbullying for both sexes ($r = 0.19 - 0.20$; $p < 0.01$) and for both educational stages ($r = 0.17 - 0.21$; $p < 0.01$). Self-concept is shown to be a protective factor for cyberbullying, therefore, addressing and working on it through the different dimensions can combat adolescent cyberbullying arising from the advance of technology and traditional bullying itself.

Keywords: cyberbullying; self-concept; student; physical education; adolescence.

Resumen

El ciberacoso es un fenómeno muy complejo derivado de la continua e inagotable evolución de las tecnologías de la información y la comunicación (TIC). Se buscan factores asociados a este fenómeno como la autoeficacia emocional, la autoestima y la empatía. Así, los objetivos fueron: (1) analizar las puntuaciones en los cuestionarios de Ciberacoso (ECIPQ) y Autoconcepto (AF-5) en función del género y la etapa educativa, (2) explorar las correlaciones entre el ciberacoso y el autoconcepto según el género y la etapa educativa. Se diseñó un estudio transversal con un total de 1155 participantes, 48.8% chicos y 51.2% chicas, donde el 75.9% cursaba Educación Secundaria Obligatoria (ESO) y el 24.1% Bachillerato. Se mostraron correlaciones medias inversas significativas entre las dimensiones del ciberacoso con el autoconcepto total para ambos sexos ($r = -0.15 - -0.11$; $p < 0.01$) y para los estudiantes de ESO ($r = -0.13 - -0.12$; $p < 0.01$), observándose estas correlaciones en los estudiantes de Bachillerato para la cibervictimización ($r = -0.14$; $p = 0.02$). Se observaron correlaciones medias inversas significativas entre el autoconcepto académico ($r = -0.25 - -0.22$; $p < 0.01 - 0.04$) y familiar ($r = -0.27 - -0.26$; $p < 0.01$) con el ciberacoso para ambos sexos y ambas etapas educativas. También se mostraron correlaciones medias directas y significativas entre el autoconcepto emocional y el ciberacoso para ambos sexos ($r = 0.19 - 0.20$; $p < 0.01$) y para ambas etapas educativas ($r = 0.17 - 0.21$; $p < 0.01$). El autoconcepto se muestra como un factor protector frente al ciberacoso, por lo que abordarlo y trabajarlo a través de las diferentes dimensiones puede combatir el ciberacoso adolescente derivado del avance de la tecnología y el propio acoso tradicional.

Palabras clave: ciberacoso; autoconcepto; estudiante; Educación Física; adolescencia.

Received: October 3, 2023

Accepted: March 11, 2024

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Introduction

For some years now, the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), coupled with their continuous and inexhaustible evolution over time, has revolutionized the forms and methods of communication between people, offering innovative ways to establish different types of relationships in today's society (Kowalski et al., 2019). It's appropriate and responsible use offers numerous benefits on a social and emotional level, however, there are also inappropriate behaviors and behaviors linked to the progressive increase in the use of ICTs and social networks, especially among the adolescent population from 13 to 17 (Kowalski et al., 2019). The easy accessibility presented by adolescents to the Internet, the continuous and daily use of different technological devices and the increase in cyberrelationships through social networks, has increased the adolescent risk of being involved in some cyberbullying event (Pieper & Pieper, 2017).

Cyberbullying

Cyberbullying is a highly complex phenomenon that is influenced by a variety of factors and, as with traditional bullying, is difficult to measure or define (Baldry et al., 2015). Smith et al. defined it as "an aggressive and intentional act carried out by an individual or group of individuals, using electronic forms of contact, repeatedly and over time against a victim who cannot easily defend himself or herself" (p. 376) (Smith et al., 2008). Although both types of bullying have similarities in that they are phenomena where a vulnerable victim, for reasons of power imbalance with respect to the bully or bullies, receives harassment, bullying, humiliation, or continuous threat for belonging to an ethnic minority group, having a disability or being homosexual or bisexual among other factors (Kowalski et al., 2019; Salmon et al., 2018). However, there are also differences, for example, in cyberbullying the anonymity on the part of the bully is one of the main differences with respect to traditional bullying, leading to greater psychological stress on the victim and benefiting bullies in the lack of face-to-face contact with the victim (Eyuboglu et al., 2021). In addition, cyberbullying can extend beyond the school day, occurring at any time of the day, in this line, the reasons for not disclosing the victimization status are also different between the two types of bullying, with cyberbullying victims expressing concern about being deprived of the technological means by which they receive cyberbullying and victims of traditional bullying fearing that the bully will find out (Agatston et al., 2007). The anonymity of the bully in cyberbullying can also make it difficult for the victim to report the bullying situation by not knowing specifically who or who is doing it (DePaolis & Williford, 2015).

The prevalences of cyberbullying are analyzed taking into account the main roles of those involved such as cyberaggressor, cybervictim and cybervictim/aggressor (Del Rey et al., 2015). Most studies show that cyberbullying prevalence rates increase with age (Chen et al., 2018; Ortega et al., 2008), increasing from childhood to middle adolescence, with a subsequent decline thereafter (Zych & Farrington, 2021). Regarding gender, several studies do not show that gender has a moderating effect (Holfeld & Mishna, 2019; Lozano-Blasco et al., 2020), however, some studies report that boys are cyberbullies (Larrañaga et al., 2018; Perren & Gutzwiller-Helfenfinger, 2012) more frequently and girls cybervictims (Baldry et al., 2019; Moreno-Ruiz et al., 2019). Overall, Brochado et al. found that lifetime victimization rates ranged from 4.9% to 65.0%, while lifetime perpetration rates ranged from 1.2% to 44.1% (Brochado et al., 2017). In Spain, prevalences vary from one community to another, in Andalusia, for example, 9.3% of students showed themselves as cybervictims, 5.5% as cyberaggressors and 3.4% as cybervictims/cyberaggressors (Fernández et al., 2016), and in Euskadi 30.2% admitted to being cybervictims, 15.5% cyberaggressors and 65.1% cyberobservers, the latter a different role to those discussed above where the person is a spectator of the cyberbullying case (Garaigordobil, 2015). These data are certainly alarming because of the impact on the social, emotional and mental well-being, especially in cyber-victims, of cyberbullying cases that occur through a variety of electronic media, but mostly associated with social networks (Giumetti & Kowalski, 2022). In this sense, cyberbullying victimization has been shown to increase levels of psychological distress and physical complaints (Albdour et al., 2019), increase depressive symptoms and anxiety (Cao et al., 2019), decrease feelings of life satisfaction (Viner et al., 2019) and even, increase suicidal ideation and suicide attempts (Sampasa & Hamilton, 2015). To assess cyberbullying, the Spanish version of the European Cyberbullying

Intervention Project Questionnaire (ECIPQ) (Del Rey et al., 2015) is used. They measure different aspects of cyberbullying: frequency, duration and severity of cyberbullying behaviours, as well as emotional and behavioural responses of the victims.

The most recent research, therefore, has focused on exploring which factors or variables are associated with the relationship between cyberbullying victimization and well-being. Along these lines, emotional self-efficacy was found to mediate the relationship between cyberbullying victimization and well-being (understood as perceived social support, self-esteem, and subjective well-being) (Ho et al., 2021). A negative connection between cybervictimization and self-esteem was also demonstrated (Extremera et al., 2018), with low self-esteem being shown in some studies to be a predictor of cybervictimization and high self-esteem a protective factor for cybervictimization (Brewer & Kerslake, 2015; Mobin et al., 2017). Regarding the relationship between cyberaggression and levels of self-esteem there is no clear consensus, showing in some studies a negative correlation where a low level of self-esteem is a predictor of aggression (Brewer & Kerslake, 2015) and in others relating a high self-esteem with a higher risk of cyberaggression (Bergmann & Baier, 2018). Furthermore, high levels of cyberaggression were associated with low levels of empathy and moral connectedness (Garaigordobil, 2017), with a stronger negative association occurring with cognitive empathy in some studies (Del Rey et al., 2016) and with affective empathy in others (Ang et al., 2017).

Self-concept

Self-concept in all its dimensions (social, emotional, academic/work, family and physical) (García et al., 2011) plays a crucial role in the self-perception of one's own development and could influence to some extent their involvement in cases of cyberbullying, either as a victim or as an aggressor (Romero-Abrio et al., 2019). Self-concept can be defined as the set of beliefs that the individual has about themselves at a given moment, influenced by the positive or negative feelings they have about themselves and by the experiences lived in their social and cultural environment that serve them to build their personality and develop emotionally and socially (Montoya et al., 2019). To assess self-concept, the AF-5 scale is used (García et al., 2011), composed of 5 dimensions: academic self-concept, social self-concept, emotional self-concept, family self-concept, physical self-concept, and physical self-concept (García et al., 2011).

Background and present study

Some research has explored this association between cyberbullying and self-concept, observing that cyberbullying victims presented a lower self-concept at a general level (Brewer & Kerslake, 2015; Extremera et al., 2018) and, specifically, a lower physical and social self-concept, with bullies showing lower scores in academic and family self-concept (Cañas et al., 2020). However, there is a paucity of studies that analyze the 5 dimensions of self-concept and their association with cyberbullying, as well as whether there are differences according to gender and educational stage. Therefore, this research aims to analyze the scores obtained by adolescents in the dimensions that make up the Cyberbullying (ECIPQ) and Self-Concept (AF-5) questionnaires as a function of gender and educational stage. In addition, we sought to explore possible correlations between cyberbullying and self-concept by analyzing the associations between the dimensions of the ECIPQ questionnaire and the final score of the AF-5 scale and the associations between the dimensions of the AF-5 scale and the ECIPQ score, both as a function of gender and educational stage.

Materials and Methods

Design

This is a cross-sectional study, carried out in Spain, specifically in the region of Extremadura (south-west Spain), whose data was collected in 2022.

Participants

The following inclusion criteria were established for the participants in this research: (1) Being a student of Physical Education at a public or subsidized secondary school in Extremadura, a Spanish

autonomous community (2), having an informed consent signed by the parent or guardian authorizing the student's participation in the research.

A non-probability sampling method based on convenience sampling was used to select the sample size (Salkind et al., 1999). The total sample ($N=1155$) consisted of 48.8% boys and 51.2% girls, showing a balanced proportion in relation to the sex of the participants. In relation to the educational stage, most of the sample was made up of students studying Compulsory Secondary Education (CSE) with 75.9%, while 24.1% were high Baccalaureate students. For the location of the center, centers located in towns with more than 20,000 inhabitants were classified as urban centers and those located in towns with less than 20,000 inhabitants as rural centers, categorization based on the criteria established by the Cáceres Provincial Council (<https://www.dip-caceres.es/>). The 31.9% belonged to rural centers and 68.1% to urban centers. In addition, 75.2% of the participants studied in public centers and 24.8% in subsidized centers. All the sociodemographic information on the participants is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Sociodemographic characteristics of the participants (N = 1155)

Variables	Categories	N	%
Gender	Boys	564	48.8
	Girls	591	51.2
Educational Stage	CSE	877	75.9
	Baccalaureate	278	24.1
Center Location	Rural	368	31.9
	Urban	787	68.1
Center type	Public	869	75.2
	Subsidized	286	24.8
Variables	Categories	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Age		14.71	1.58

Note. *N*: number; %: percentage; *M*: Mean; *SD*: Standard deviation

Instruments

The instrument used to profile the sample was a socio-demographic questionnaire containing questions on gender, age, use of electronic devices, cyberbullying and physical activity.

The Spanish version of the European Cyberbullying Intervention Project Questionnaire (ECIPQ) was used to assess cyberbullying (Del Rey et al., 2015). It consists of 22 items that measure different aspects of cyberbullying, including the frequency, duration, and severity of cyberbullying behaviors. The questionnaire also includes items that measure the emotional and behavioral responses of victims of cyberbullying. The score is a Likert scale ranging from 0 (never) to 4 (always). This instrument has reliability indices of 0.87 for victimisation and 0.88 for aggression.

The AF-5 scale (García et al., 2011) was used to evaluate self-concept, consisting of a total of 30 items covering 5 dimensions: academic self-concept; social self-concept; emotional self-concept; family self-concept; physical self-concept. A Likert scale of 1 to 5 is used, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 5 means "strongly agree". In relation to the psychometric properties of the instrument, in each of the five dimensions, the authors reported that the AF-5 scale offers indices higher than 0.71. Taking all the items of the scale as a whole, it was shown that all items measure the same construct (self-concept), obtaining a value of 0.78.

Procedure

The database of the Department of Education and Employment of the Regional Government of Extremadura was used in order to know the educational centers in which Physical Education is taught from Primary Education to High School (from 8 to 18 years old) and thus be able to collect the necessary data to compose the sample. Physical Education teachers were contacted via e-mail. Using the same means, the teachers who wanted to collaborate in the research were asked to reply to the e-mail, so that an appointment could be arranged, and a researcher could come to the center to administer the questionnaires. The questionnaires could only be completed by students who had submitted the informed consent form signed by their parents or guardians. The e-mail provided information on the objectives of the research, an informed consent form to be signed by parents or guardians, and a model of the questionnaires to be used (sociodemographic, ECIPQ and AF-5). Each student was given a Tablet where he/she could fill in the questionnaires through the Google Forms application. In order to avoid any doubts when answering the questionnaires, the questions were explained one by one. Once the data from all the questionnaires had been collected, the researchers proceeded to curate, process and anonymize the data. Subsequently, another researcher would perform the blind statistical analysis.

In this research, a protocol was followed taking into account the considerations of the Declaration of Helsinki. This protocol was approved by the Biosafety and Bioethics Committee of the University of Extremadura in Spain (Registration Code 72/2022).

Statistical analysis

The Statal Package of Social Science (SPSS) version 23 for MAC (IBM SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA) was used to process the data collected. First, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to explore the assumption of normality in the distribution of the data of the continuous variables. It was found that this assumption was not met, so it was decided to use nonparametric statistical tests.

In order to analyze the possible differences in the scores of the dimensions according to the gender and educational stage of the students, both in the ECIPQ and the AF-5, the U-Mann Whitney statistical test was used. Similarly, Spearman's Rho test was used to analyze the relationship between the scores of each of the dimensions of the questionnaires. To interpret the correlation coefficients, the thresholds proposed by Mondragón-Barrera (Barrera, 2014) were followed: from 0.01 to 0.10 (low correlation), from 0.11 to 0.50 (medium correlation), from 0.51 to 0.75 (considerable correlation), from 0.76 to 0.90 (very high correlation) and from 0.91 to 1.00 (perfect correlation). Finally, Cronbach's alpha was used to analyze reliability for each of the instruments. To interpret the values of the reliability test, we took as a reference those given by Nunnally Bernstein (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994): <0.70 (low), 0.71 to 0.90 (satisfactory) and >0.91 (excellent).

Results

Table 2 shows both the descriptive statistics and the differences obtained in the two dimensions of the ECIPQ and the AF-5 according to gender and the educational stage to which the students belong. At a general level, women show higher scores in the victimization dimension of the ECIPQ and similar values in the second dimension; however, no statistically significant differences were observed in any of them. On the other hand, participants who belonged to Baccalaureate showed higher scores in both dimensions compared to CSE students, although significant differences were only found in the one referring to abusive behaviors. Significant differences were found in all dimensions of the AF-5 when comparing the scores obtained according to gender. Women, on the other hand, obtain higher scores in the dimensions referring to academic and emotional aspects, while men seem to have better perceptions regarding their social, family and physical self-concept. With respect to educational level, significant differences were only found in the dimension referring to emotional self-concept, with Baccalaureate students showing the highest scores.

Table 2

Descriptive results of the ECIPQ and the AF-5 according to gender and educational stage of the participants

ECIPQ and AF-5 Dimensions	Gender			Educational Stage		
	Boys	Girls	<i>p</i>	CSE	Baccalaureate	<i>p</i>
	Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)		Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)	
1) ECIPQ-Victim	1.09 (0.36)	1.18 (0.36)	0.09	1.09 (0.36)	1.18 (0.36)	0.71
2) ECIPQ-Abuser	1.00 (0.18)	1.00 (0.18)	0.45	1.00 (0.18)	1.09 (0.27)	<0.01* *
1) AF-5 Academic	3.66 (1.17)	3.83 (1.04)	<0.01**	3.66 (1.00)	3.66 (1.17)	0.59
2) AF-5 Social	4.00 (0.83)	3.83 (1.00)	<0.01**	3.83 (1.00)	3.83 (0.83)	0.16
3) AF-5 Emotional	2.33 (0.83)	3.00 (1.17)	<0.01**	2.66 (1.00)	2.83 (1.17)	<0.01* *
4) AF-5 Family	4.66 (0.83)	4.50 (1.00)	<0.01**	4.66 (1.00)	4.50 (1.04)	0.08
5) AF-5 Physical	3.83 (1.00)	3.33 (1.00)	<0.01**	3.50 (1.00)	3.50 (1.17)	0.44

Note: Me = median value; IQR = interquartile range. Differences are significant at ***p* < 0.01; **p* < 0.05. Each score is obtained is based on a Likert scale (0–4): 0 is “Never” and 4 “Always”.

Table 3 indicates the associations found between the ECIPQ dimensions and the final score of the AF-5, showing both significant, inverse and mean correlations at the overall level. Likewise, the results by gender show correlations of similar characteristics, being slightly higher in female students. In addition, all correlations when examining educational stage were mean, inverse and significant, except for the second dimension of the ECIPQ at the Baccalaureate stage where the minimum level of significance was not reached. The first dimension of the ECIPQ, on the other hand, manifested a higher correlation with the AF-5 in the Baccalaureate stage when compared to those participants in the CSE.

Table 3

Correlations between ECIPQ dimensions and AF-5 scores, according to gender and educational stage of the student body

ECIPQ Dimensions	AF-5 <i>ρ</i> (<i>p</i>)	Gender		Educational Stage	
		Boys	Girls	CSE	Baccalaureate
		Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)
1) ECIPQ-Victim	-0.15 (<0.01)**	-0.12 (<0.01)**	-0.15 (<0.01)**	-0.13 (<0.01)**	-0.14 (0.02)*
2) ECIPQ-Abuser	-0.12 (<0.01)**	-0.11 (0.01)*	-0.13 (<0.01)**	-0.12 (<0.01)**	-0.11 (0.09)

Me = median value; IQR = interquartile range. Differences are significant at ***p* < 0.01; **p* < 0.05.

Likewise, in the present study, the correlations between the dimensions of the AF-5 and the ECIPQ score were explored (Table 4). In general, the dimensions related to academic and family aspects showed medium, inverse and significant correlations. As for social and physical self-concept, they showed inverse and low relationships, although only physical characteristics showed statistical significance. Finally, for emotional traits the association was significant, medium and positive.

Regarding gender, the only dimension that did not show significant correlations was the social component. Similarly, the physical dimension does not seem to be related to the scores obtained by men. The academic aspects show inverse, medium and significant correlations, with the values of women being slightly higher than those of men, as is also the case in the family dimension. Finally, emotional traits have slightly higher mean, direct and significant associations in men.

If we focus on the educational stage, once again, the social aspects did not show any significance, as did the physical dimension in the CSE students. For academic and emotional characteristics, correlations were inverse, medium and significant, with higher association in CSE

students. Similarly, CSE students show higher correlations than high school students in the dimension referring to emotional aspects, being direct and average.

Table 4

Correlations between AF-5 dimensions and ECIPQ scores, according to gender and educational stage of the student body

AF-5 Dimensions	ECIPQ ρ (p)	Gender		Educational Stage	
		Boys	Girls	CSE	Baccalaureate
		Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)	Me (IQR)
1) Academic	-0.22 (<0.01)**	-0.22 (<0.01)**	-0.23 (<0.01)**	-0.25 (<0.01)**	-0.12 (0.04)*
2) Social	-0.04 (0.14)	-0.07 (0.08)	-0.01 (0.90)	-0.04 (0.22)	-0.05 (0.43)
3) Emotional	0.20 (<0.01)**	0.20 (<0.01)**	0.19 (<0.01)**	0.21 (<0.01)**	0.17 (<0.01)**
4) Family	-0.32 (<0.01)**	-0.27 (<0.01)**	-0.36 (<0.01)**	-0.33 (<0.01)**	-0.28 (<0.01)**
5) Physical	-0.08 (0.01)*	-0.04 (0.40)	-0.09 (0.03)*	-0.05 (0.17)	-0.17 (<0.01)**

Note: Me = median value; IQR = interquartile range. Differences are significant at ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

The linear regression analysis of the participants' Cyberbullying is summarized in Table 5 (ECIPQ-Victim) and Table 6 (ECIPQ-Abuser). The analysis included as independent variables academic self-concept, social self-concept, Educational Stage, emotional self-concept, family self-concept, physical self-concept, gender, age, school environment, and type of school. Model 1 in Table 4 indicates the proportion of variance in the 'ECIPQ-Victim' variable explained by the included independent variables (11%), and Model 1 in Table 5 shows the proportion of variance in the 'ECIPQ-Abuser' variable explained by the included independent variables (5%).

Table 5

ECIPQ-Victim prediction model

ECIPQ-Victim		Model 1 (R^2) = 0.11		
Variable	β	SE	t	p
Familiar	-0.151	0.016	-9.205	<0.001
Emotional	0.094	0.015	6.107	<0.001
Physical	0.042	0.016	2.529	0.012
Sex	-0.057	0.025	-2.273	0.023
Constant	1.552	0.099	15.685	<0.001

Table 6

ECIPQ-Abuser prediction model

ECIPQ-Abuser		Model 1 (R^2) = 0.05		
Variable	β	SE	t	p
Sexo	-0.041	0.020	-2.100	0.036
Familiar	-0.080	0.013	-6.196	<0.001
Físico	0.041	0.013	3.191	0.001
Emocional	0.043	0.012	3.557	<0.001
Constant	1.265	0.078	16.305	<0.001

The regression analysis shows that the ability of both models to explain the variability in the ECIPQ-Victim and ECIPQ-Abuser is limited ($R^2 = 0.11$ and $R^2 = 0.05$), suggesting that other variables or factors with impact need to be explored.

Finally, the Cronbach's alpha values for the ECIPQ dimensions were 0.874 for the victimization dimension and 0.879 for the abuser factor, therefore, they are considered satisfactory. In addition, the AF-5 values can also be considered as satisfactory (Academic = 0.878; Social = 0.758; Emotional = 0.801; Family = 0.879; and Physical = 0.763).

Discussion

The aim of this research was to analyze scores on the Cyberbullying (ECIPQ) and Self-Concept (AF-5) questionnaires as a function of gender and educational stage, (2) to explore the correlations between cyberbullying and self-concept as a function of gender and educational stage. First, in this study, no significant gender differences were observed in either the victim or aggressor dimensions of cyberbullying. However, scores on the victim dimension were slightly higher in girls than in boys, with both sexes showing the same scores for the aggressor dimension. These results are in line with other research where no significant differences were demonstrated between boys and girls and adolescents in their participation in cyberbullying, both as cybervictims (Álvarez-García et al., 2016) and cyberaggressors (Álvarez et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2017). However, girls obtained slightly higher scores than boys in cybervictimization, this could be explained by the empathic nature of girls and the lower probability of being involved in violent contexts that encourage doing some kind of harm to others (Mestre et al., 2009). In contrast, other studies found that boys were cyberbullies more often (Larrañaga et al., 2018; Perren & Gutzwiller, 2012) and that cybervictimization may be more frequent in girls (Baldry et al., 2019; Moreno et al., 2019). As for the educational stage, no significant differences were observed in the cybervictimization dimension, but they were found in the dimension referring to cyberbullying, with Baccalaureate students showing slightly higher scores than those in CSE. This is somewhat related to what happened in other studies, where it was observed that cyberbullying increased with age (González et al., 2020; Machimbarrena et al., 2018). This situation could be related to the fact that adolescents as they get older, enjoy more opportunities, access and time to interact with their electronic devices, showing greater autonomy and less adult supervision (Law et al., 2010; Sticca et al., 2013).

For self-concept, in this study, significant differences were observed in terms of sex in the five dimensions of which the AF-5 questionnaire is composed, with girls showing a better academic and emotional self-concept than boys and boys showing a better physical, family and social self-concept than girls. In relation to academic self-concept most studies show how girls present a better self-concept than boys (González et al., 2020; Malo et al., 2011; Meza & Pompa, 2015). In this sense, the greater self-demand, dedication and effort at the academic level of girls (Jiménez et al., 2007), together with the fact that their better study habits tend to make them get better grades than boys (Seder & Villalonga, 2016), could influence this better academic self-concept, since girls have been shown to attribute their academic success to effort and boys to the skills, they have (Inglés et al., 2012). At the level of emotional self-concept, the results of this research differ with those observed in other research where boys show a better emotional self-concept than girls (Amado-Alonso et al., 2018; Cachón et al., 2020; González et al., 2020; Herrera et al., 2020), this could be explained and be related to the differences found in other studies in relation to emotional intelligence where there is no clear consensus. In some research, it is observed that men seem to manage their negative emotions better (Berrocal & Extremera, 2008) and other studies show that women have better emotional skills than men (Joseph & Newman, 2010). Regarding family and social self-concept, the results of this research are also contrary to what has been observed in previous studies, where it is shown that girls present a better family and social self-concept or no significant differences are found between both sexes (Amado et al., 2018; González-Valero et al., 2020; Malo Cerrato et al., 2011; Meza & Pompa, 2015). In a study by Herrera et al., (2020) girls showed a higher family and social self-concept due to better social skills such as empathy and social responsibility, and boys showed a higher emotional self-concept due to better emotional skills such as stress tolerance and impulse control (Herrera et al., 2020). In addition, gender differences in social and family self-concept could be due to the treatment received by parents and the close environment (Herrera et al., 2020). What happened with physical self-concept does follow the line of previous studies, with boys showing a better physical self-concept than girls (Cachón et al., 2020; Malo et al., 2011; Meza &

Pompa, 2015). This difference could be associated with biological causes or along stereotypical sex role lines, where boys tend to achieve higher performance in most physical skills, showing greater muscle density than girls (Babic et al., 2014). Another possible justification could be related to physiological changes associated with puberty, appearing earlier in girls than in boys (Li et al., 2018). In this sense, girls might try to hide these changes, considering them unattractive (Vermeir & Van, 2014) and potentially negatively affecting their physical self-concept. In relation to the educational stage, no significant differences were observed for any dimension of self-concept between CSE and Baccalaureate students, with the exception of emotional self-concept, with a better emotional self-concept being observed in Baccalaureate students. The scores between both stages are very similar and the scarcity of difference could be due to the fact that the age difference between both stages may not be sufficient or influential, contrary to what could occur between primary and secondary education, since in secondary school psychological and emotional alterations occur that build the self-concept and personality of the individual (Onetti et al., 2019).

At a general level, cybervictimization and cyberabuse were inversely correlated with the total AF-5 self-concept scale score, i.e., the higher the adolescent's self-concept, the lower the cybervictimization and cyberabuse. These correlations were average and significant for both sexes, with girls showing a slightly higher correlation in both dimensions of the ECIPQ. In relation to educational stage, the correlations were also average and significant for both stages, except for the cyberabuse dimension in Baccalaureate where the correlations were not significant. In the cybervictimization dimension, Baccalaureate students showed a slightly higher correlation than CSE students. These findings are related to what happened in other studies where cybervictimization was associated with low self-concept (Brewer & Kerlake, 2015; Extremera et al., 2018; Romero et al., 2019; Wachs et al., 2016), i.e., a higher self-concept could be seen as a protective effect on cyberbullying victimization. In this sense, other studies that analyze the relationship between cybervictimization and factors that influence the construction of adolescent self-concept also support the results of this research, as is the case of family support and positive parent-adolescent relationship (Fridh et al., 2015; Martins et al., 2016), perceived peer support (Baldry et al., 2015; Kowalski et al., 2014), self-efficacy to defend oneself (Chen et al., 2017), and self-esteem (Brewer & Kerlake, 2015; Mobin et al., 2017). In the case of cyberbullying, self-concept is shown to be a predictor of cyberbullying abusive behaviors in this study. In this line, other research supports to some extent this result, as cyberabuse is also related to variables that shape self-concept in adolescents such as empathy and moral connectedness (Baldry et al., 2015; Brewer & Kerlake, 2015; Del Rey et al., 2016; Garaigordobil, 2017), self-efficacy (Chen et al., 2017), levels of self-control and impulsivity (Antoniadou et al., 2016; Baldry et al., 2015), and social isolation and peer rejection (Baldry et al., 2015; Bayraktar et al., 2015).

In general, correlations were established between the different dimensions that make up the self-concept and the total score of the ECIPQ questionnaire, with mean and negative correlations for academic and family self-concept and mean and positive correlations for emotional self-concept. This means that a higher family and academic self-concept meant lower participation in cyberbullying either as a bully or a victim and, that a higher emotional self-concept translated into higher participation in cyberbullying itself. As for social and physical self-concept, correlations were not significant for social and physical self-concept showed negative and low correlations. For gender, the correlations are similar to those previously mentioned, with the exception of physical self-concept in boys where the correlation was not significant. Boys showed slightly elevated correlations in emotional self-concept and girls in academic, family and physical self-concept. For the educational stage the correlations are similar to the general ones, however, in the physical self-concept the correlations were not significant for the CSE students. In CSE students, higher correlations were observed in academic, emotional and family self-concept than in Baccalaureate students. The most striking finding is the direct relationship between emotional self-concept and cyberbullying, as in other research the levels of self-esteem (Brewer & Kerlake, 2015; Mobin et al., 2017), empathy (Baldry et al., 2015; Brewer & Kerlake, 2015; Del Rey et al., 2016; Garaigordobil, 2017) and the ability to control emotions and impulses (Antoniadou et al., 2016; Baldry et al., 2015), factors that make up the emotional self-concept, were inversely related to victimization and abusive behaviors in cyberbullying, understanding these as protective factors contrary

to what happens in this study. Regarding academic and family self-concept and its inverse relationship with cyberbullying, the Romero (2019) et al. study supports these results, showing that adolescents with low cyberbullying status reported higher family and academic self-concept. In other studies self-concept along with family functioning has been highlighted as a protective factor against cybervictimization (Kowalski et al., 2019), in addition to the importance of frequent parent-child communication in increasing the self-concept levels of adolescents (Özdemir, 2014). For academic self-concept, Romero et al. (2019) in agreement with our results, show how when students, especially girls, are victimized, their academic self-concept is reduced. This lower academic self-concept as suggested by other research, could be related to adjustment variables such as anxiety, academic performance and intrinsic motivation (Khalaila, 2015), observing at the same time that these variables are significantly associated with cyberbullying (Litwiller & Brausch, 2013).

Practical implications

It is important to use scientific evidence in the education system (Sánchez et al., 2022) in order to move towards quality education. The present research has shown the association between adolescent self-concept and being involved in cyberbullying, either as a victim or as an aggressor. It is suggested that policies and programs be implemented and developed taking into account these findings, where adolescents can obtain or apply tools to work on their self-concept in the different dimensions that compose it. This improved self-concept could be a great protector against cyberbullying, as the use and advancement of ICTs is likely to continue to increase, at the same time as the ease and time of access to electronic devices continues to increase among adolescents (Kowalski et al., 2019). As we have seen, self-concept and its different dimensions are built from different factors, where the educational center could exert some influence from a process of teaching-learning competence based on their interests and motivations, as well as families that provide support, positive perceptions and protection in the adolescent (Özdemir, 2014).

Limitations and future prospects

The results should be interpreted with caution because this is a cross-sectional and correlational study, where it is not possible to establish causal relationships between variables. In this line, it would be interesting to continue investigating these findings, and a longitudinal study could be carried out with measurements at different times in order to establish the observed relationships.

The sample was composed of students from Extremadura, a Spanish autonomous community; therefore, it would be innovative to replicate this type of study in other Spanish regions or in other countries, checking and analyzing whether there are sociocultural differences.

The role of the bystander witness was not taken into account in this study because the employee questionnaire did not collect it. Other research could study this role and its possible association with self-concept, as the fear of defending the victim for becoming a new target of the stalker could influence in some sense (Myers & Cowie, 2019; Purdy & York, 2016).

Another possible line of research to propose could be to study the influence of emotional intelligence between the dimensions of self-concept and cyberbullying (Torres et al., 2023).

Conclusions

No significant differences were obtained for both dimensions of cyberbullying as a function of gender and for educational stage, Baccalaureate students showed greater cyberbullying behavior than CSE students. A higher academic and emotional self-concept was observed in girls and a higher social, family and physical self-concept in boys. Cybervictimization and cyberbullying were associated with self-concept for both sexes and for CSE students, but for Baccalaureate students only self-concept was associated with cybervictimization. Inverse associations were shown between academic and family self-concept with cyberbullying for both sexes and for both educational stages. In addition, emotional self-concept was positively correlated with cyberbullying for both educational stages and both sexes. The correlation between physical self-concept and cyberbullying was low and inverse in females and medium and inverse in Baccalaureate students. These findings show how self-concept can be a

protective factor for cyberbullying and its work and improvement from the different dimensions that make up the self-concept could be a means to combat this harmful adolescent behavior arising from the advancement of technology and traditional bullying itself.

Author Contributions: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of University of Extremadura (protocol code 72/2022) for studies involving humans.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all parents of subjects involved in the study.

Data Availability Statement: The datasets are available through the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Acknowledgments: Thanks to the participant's schools, P.E. teachers, parents, and students. And also, thanks to research visit at the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid-Facultad de Ciencias de la Actividad Física y del Deporte-INEF (24-08-2023/24-10-2023) by the second author of this research report.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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